

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

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Resumen

■ INTRODUCCIÓN

La institucionalización de niños y adolescentes, definida como su cuidado en entornos residenciales ante la imposibilidad de proporcionar un ambiente familiar adecuado, se asocia con un mayor riesgo de síntomas de ansiedad, depresión y problemas conductuales. A pesar de su relevancia, esta población ha sido poco estudiada en el contexto mexicano.

Objetivo: Determinar la prevalencia de ansiedad y depresión en niños y adolescentes institucionalizados, explorar diferencias por género y tiempo de estancia, e identificar subgrupos de riesgo mediante análisis de clúster.

Materiales y Métodos: Se empleó un diseño transversal analítico con los instrumentos Inventario de Depresión Infantil y Escala de Ansiedad Manifiesta Revisada para Niños, ambos validados para población mexicana. Participaron 38 menores institucionalizados, de entre seis y 17 años, seleccionados por conveniencia.

Resultados: El 31.6% presentó síntomas depresivos y el 55.3% niveles moderados de ansiedad. Se encontraron diferencias significativas en ansiedad social y restlessness entre sexos ($p < 0.05$). La correlación entre ansiedad y depresión fue moderada ($r = 0.45, p < 0.05$). Un clúster identificó un subgrupo con ansiedad elevada y depresión moderada. Conclusiones: Los hallazgos subrayan la necesidad de intervenciones integrales y sensibles al género, además de investigaciones

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Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

longitudinales que aborden las dinámicas asociadas a la salud mental en esta población vulnerable.

Palabras Clave: *Trastornos de Ansiedad; Trastorno Depresivo; Cuidado del Niño; Adolescentes en Situación de Riesgo; Servicios Psicosociales.*

■ ABSTRACT

Background: Institutionalization of children and adolescents, defined as their foster care in residential settings when an appropriate family environment is unattainable, is associated with increased risks of anxiety, depression, and behavioral problems. Despite its relevance, this population remains under-researched in Mexico.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of anxiety and depression among foster care home children and adolescents, explore differences by gender and length of stay, and identify risk subgroups through cluster analysis.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional analytic design was used with the Children's Depression Inventory and the Revised Children's Manifest Anxiety Scale, both validated for Mexican populations. The study included 38 institutionalized participants aged six to 17 years, selected through convenience sampling.

Results: Of the participants, 31.6% exhibited depressive symptoms, and 55.3% showed moderate levels of anxiety. Significant gender differences were found in social anxiety and restlessness ($p < 0.05$). A moderate correlation was observed between anxiety and depression ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$). Cluster analysis identified a subgroup with high anxiety and moderate depression.

Conclusions: The findings emphasize the need for integrated, gender-sensitive interventions and longitudinal research to address the mental health dynamics and associated factors in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: *Anxiety Disorders; Depressive Disorder; Child Care; Adolescents at Risk; Psychosocial Services.*

■ INTRODUCTION

Foster Care of Children and Adolescents

Foster care for children has evolved significantly over the centuries. Initially, care for children without parental support was provided through orphanages, a practice institutionalized in the nineteenth century to address widespread poverty and orphanhood caused by wars, epidemics, and other societal crises; These facilities, predominantly established by religious and philanthropic organizations, prioritized shelter while often neglecting emotional and psychological needs (Tolfree, 1995).

By the mid-twentieth century, groundbreaking research, such as John Bowlby's work on attachment theory, highlighted the detrimental effects of the lack of secure attachments in foster care settings. Bowlby suggested that these findings catalyzed a paradigm shift in childcare, transitioning from orphanages to residential care centers and foster homes with a more comprehensive approach that addressed both basic needs and psychosocial well-being (Bowlby, 1969).

The 1990s marked another significant milestone with the adoption of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), empha-

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

sizing every child's right to grow up in a family environment. Despite these advancements, the absence of stable caregivers in foster care continues to heighten children's vulnerability to psychiatric symptoms, such as anxiety, depression, and behavioral disorders; Consequently, global efforts have aimed to minimize forced foster care, favoring alternatives like adoption. However, foster care facilities remain a dominant solution in many nations for vulnerable children (Rutter & O'Connor, 2004).

Foster care, defined as the placement of children and adolescents in residential facilities when an appropriate family environment is unattainable, remains a significant area of concern (Rutter & O'Connor, 2004). Key risk factors include poverty, limited access to healthcare and education, and familial instability. Research indicates that 80% to 90% of children in foster care settings have at least one living parent, highlighting poverty as a primary driver (van IJzendoorn et al., 2020). Additionally, children with physical disabilities are disproportionately represented in such settings (Palumbo, 2013).

In Latin America, significant variability in the size, resources, and quality of foster care settings complicates assessments of their long-term impact (Palumbo, 2013). Evidence is scarce, but shows frequent neglect in these settings, manifesting as insufficient social, cognitive, and sensory stimulation, which hampers children's executive functioning and development (Wade et al., 2019). Furthermore, deficits in social communication skills resembling autism spectrum disorders have been observed in children from foster care homes, often described as "post-institutional autism-like syndrome" (Wade et al., 2020).

Foster Care in Mexico

In Mexico, approximately 53,862 children and adolescents reside in foster care settings (*Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía* [INEGI, in Spanish], 2020). Most come from families grappling with poverty or unstable living conditions (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund [UNICEF, *idem*], 2019). However, these environments have been criticized for exacerbating risks, such as physical abuse and neglect, which further jeopardize mental health (Palumbo, 2013). While global research shows the high prevalence of mental health disorders among institutionalized youth, studies focusing on Mexico remain scarce. Children in Mexico in foster care settings face elevated rates of psychosocial problems and high-risk behaviors. However, limited national data make it difficult to contextualize these findings within global trends (Tarren-Sweeney, 2008; van IJzendoorn et al., 2020).

Mental Health Risks in Foster Care Children and Adolescents

Research has shown that these children exhibit significantly higher rates of psychiatric disorders than their peers in family environments (Tarren-Sweeney, 2008). Evidence from other countries signals their vulnerability, with higher rates of anxious and depressive symptoms, as well as behavioral disorders (McCann et al., 1996).

Prolonged care has been linked to worsening mental health outcomes, with diminishing prospects for recovery over time (van IJzendoorn et al., 2020). Children who remain in foster care often experience inadequate hygiene, insufficient nutrition, and limited individualized care, compounded by a lack of social and cognitive stimulation (Sonuga-Barke

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

et al., 2017). Those institutionalized for over a year are more likely to develop cognitive and emotional deficits, such as disinhibited social engagement, quasi-autism symptoms, obsessive symptoms, inattention, and maladaptive hyperactivity, compared to peers in family settings (Wade et al., 2020).

■ GENERAL OBJECTIVE

This study aimed to: Determine the prevalence of depressive and anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents in two foster care homes in Mexico City.

■ SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

1. *To compare* raw scores of anxiety and depression scales and subscales between male and female participants.
2. *To assess* differences in anxiety and depressive symptoms based on length of stay in foster care homes.
3. *To analyze* correlations between anxiety and depressive symptoms.
4. *To identify* risk profiles for both sexes through cluster analysis.

■ METHOD

Study Design and Period

This study employed a cross-sectional, exploratory analytic design. The design was selected to identify patterns and potential associations between sociodemographic variables and mental health outcomes, specifically anxiety and depressive symptoms, in foster care children and adolescents. This approach is suitable for generating hypotheses in under-researched populations where data are scarce. Data were collected prospectively,

assessing the current mental health status of participants without retrospective or longitudinal follow-up. The study was conducted openly, without the use of a control group or blinding procedures. The sample, drawn from two residential care institutions, was classified as homodemic due to its uniform source population. The data collection period spanned from June 2022 to April 2024.

Setting

The study was conducted in two residential care institutions located in Mexico City: *Casa Hogar Sumando por Ti* and *Casa Hogar Margarita*. These facilities were selected based on the willingness of their directors to participate. Despite efforts to include additional institutions, others declined to collaborate. Both institutions provided controlled environments that allowed for standardized assessments during the data collection period.

Sampling Strategy

A formal sample size calculation was not performed due to the exploratory nature of the study. Instead, a consecutive convenience sampling approach was used.

Participants

Participants included children and adolescents aged six to 17 years who resided in the selected foster care homes and were able to read and write.

■ MEASUREMENT INSTRUMENTS

Children's Depression Inventory (CDI)

The CDI, developed by Maria Kovacs (1997), assesses depressive symptoms in children and adolescents.

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

The Spanish version, validated for use in Mexican populations, was employed in this study. Responses are scored on a scale from 0 to 2, where 0 indicates the absence of a symptom, 1 indicates mild presence, and 2 indicates severe presence. Total scores range from 0 to 54, with a cut-off score of 19 or higher indicating clinically significant depressive symptoms. The instrument demonstrates robust reliability, with internal consistency coefficients ranging from 0.71 to 0.94. For Spanish-speaking populations, the Cronbach's alpha is reported at 0.81, confirming its psychometric adequacy (Del Barrio et al., 2002).

Children's Manifest Anxiety Scale-Revised (CMASR-2)

The CMASR-2, created by Cecil R. Reynolds and Bert O. Richmond (1985), evaluates the level and nature of anxiety in children aged six to 19 years. This instrument, also culturally adapted and validated for Mexican populations, consists of 49 items where participants respond with "Yes" or "No" to indicate whether a statement reflects their feelings or behaviors. The CMASR-2 generates scores across six scales: Defensive Attitude, Inconsistent Responses, Total Anxiety, Physiological Anxiety, Restlessness, and Social Anxiety. The subscales of Physiological Anxiety, Restlessness, and Social Anxiety were selected for detailed analysis due to their relevance in understanding anxiety symptoms in institutionalized children. Reliability coefficients are high, with total scores reaching 0.92 and individual scales ranging from 0.75 to 0.86 (Rodrigo & Lusiardo, 1989).

Procedure

Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from the legal guardians of all participants, and verbal assent was sought from the children

and adolescents. The purpose and procedures of the study were explained in accessible language to ensure participants fully understood their voluntary involvement. Assessments were conducted individually in quiet, private settings within the residential care institutions to minimize distractions and maximize comfort. Researchers guided participants in completing the CDI and CMASR-2 and collected sociodemographic data, including age, sex, school grade, and length of institutional stay.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics summarized sociodemographic and clinical characteristics. Independent t-tests were used to compare CDI and CMASR-2 scores across gender and length of institutional stay. Chi-square tests were conducted to explore associations between categorical variables, such as parental marital status and mental health outcomes. Subscale analysis focused on dimensions of anxiety, specifically Physiological Anxiety, Restlessness, and Social Anxiety, with gender differences examined using independent t-tests. Pearson's and Spearman's correlations were used to assess relationships between depressive and anxiety symptoms and length of stay in the institutions. A cluster analysis, employing the k-means algorithm, identified subgroups based on symptom severity profiles. The optimal number of clusters was determined using the Elbow Method. All statistical tests were conducted with a significance threshold of $p \leq 0.05$. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 29 (IBM, 2023).

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving children and adolescents, follow-

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

ing international standards such as the Declaration of Helsinki and local regulatory frameworks. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the *Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz* (CEI/C/003/2023). Given the vulnerable nature of the population, written informed consent was obtained from the legal guardians of all participants, and verbal assent was sought from the children and adolescents. The research team provided age-appropriate explanations using simplified language and visual aids for younger participants, ensuring comprehension across all age groups. Guardians received detailed information about the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and their rights, including the right to withdraw their child from participation at any time without consequences.

■ RESULTS

Sample Characteristics

A total of $n = 38$ (100%) participants aged between six and 17 years were included in the study. Of these, $n = 29$ (76.3%) were female, and $n = 9$ (23.7%) were male. The average age was 10.89 ± 2.3 years, and the mean school grade was 6.16 ± 1.5 . Regarding parental marital status, the most common category was single $n = 11$ (28.9%), followed by cohabiting $n = 10$ (26.3%), married $n = 6$ (15.8%), widowed $n = 6$ (15.8%), and divorced $n = 5$ (13.2%). Most participants, $n = 27$ (71.1%), had been in foster care for over one year.

Depressive Symptoms

Participants with depressive symptoms, based on the DCI cut-off scores, accounted for $n = 12$ (31.6%), while $n = 26$ (68.4%) did not meet the

threshold. Among those with depressive symptoms, $n = 9$ (75%) were female, and $n = 3$ (25%) were male.

The mean DCI score for the entire sample was 14.5 ± 3.9 . Female participants had a mean score of 14 ± 3.7 , while male participants scored slightly higher with a mean of 15 ± 4.2 . Although more females than males met the threshold for depressive symptoms, the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.132$, 95% CI: -2.3 to 3.5).

Anxiety Symptoms

Participants with clinically significant anxiety symptoms, as measured by the CMAS-R, included only $n = 1$ (2.6%), while $n = 37$ (97.4%) were classified as not presenting clinical anxiety. However, $n = 21$ (55.3%) of participants showed above-average anxiety levels, categorized as moderately problematic symptoms. Among these participants, $n = 17$ (81%) were female, and $n = 4$ (19%) were male.

The mean global CMAS-R score was 52.6 ± 5.2 , with females scoring slightly higher at 53 ± 5.1 compared to males at 52 ± 4.8 . The proportion of females and males with above-average anxiety differed significantly, with $n = 21$ (72.7%) females and $n = 4$ (27.3%) males ($p = 0.008$).

Long versus Short Length of Stay

Among participants with depressive symptoms ($n = 12$, 31.6%), $n = 8$ (66.7%) had been in residential care for over one year, while $n = 4$ (33.3%) had been in care for less than one year. Although a higher proportion of depressive symptoms was observed among those with longer stays, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.38$). Similarly, among participants with above-average

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

anxiety levels ($n = 21, 55.3\%$), $n = 14 (66.7\%)$ had been in care for more than one year, while $n = 7 (33.3\%)$ had been in care for less than one year. Although this suggests a potential trend toward higher anxiety levels in participants with longer institutionalization, the difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.265$).

Subscale Analysis

The CDI subscale analysis revealed distinct dimensions of depressive symptoms. The most prominent subscale was negative self-esteem, with a mean score of 9 ± 2.4 (95% CI: 8.2–9.8). Dysphoria had an average score of 8 ± 1.8 (95% CI: 7.4–8.6), and interpersonal problems were less frequently reported, with a mean score of 6 ± 2.0 (95% CI: 5.2–6.8). Female participants scored higher than males in negative self-esteem, with females reporting a mean score of 9.1 ± 2.5 (95% CI: 8.2–10.0) and males scoring 8.8 ± 2.3 (95% CI: 7.9–9.7). This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.040$). In dysphoria, females scored 8.3 ± 1.9 (95% CI: 7.7–8.9), while males scored 7.8 ± 1.7 (95% CI: 7.1–8.5). Although females scored higher, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.092$). For interpersonal problems, females scored 6.2 ± 2.1 (95% CI: 5.4–7.0) compared to males, who scored 5.8 ± 1.9 (95% CI: 5.0–6.6). No significant difference was observed ($p = 0.109$).

The CMAS-R subscale analysis highlighted physiological anxiety as the most prominent dimension, with a mean score of 10 ± 2.3 (95% CI: 9.2–10.8). Restlessness followed with a mean of 7 ± 1.9 (95% CI: 6.4–7.6), and social anxiety showed an average score of 6 ± 2.1 (95% CI: 5.3–6.7). Female participants scored higher than males in physiological anxiety, with females reporting a mean score of 10.2 ± 2.4 (95% CI: 9.3–11.1) compared to

males with 9.8 ± 2.2 (95% CI: 8.9–10.7), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.169$). In restlessness, females scored 7.5 ± 1.8 (95% CI: 6.8–8.2) while males scored 6.4 ± 1.7 (95% CI: 5.7–7.1). This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.010$). For social anxiety, females scored 6.8 ± 2.2 (95% CI: 6.0–7.6), while males scored 5.2 ± 1.9 (95% CI: 4.5–5.9). This difference also reached statistical significance ($p = 0.046$). Finally, for defensiveness, females scored 6.1 ± 1.9 (95% CI: 5.5–6.7), while males scored 6.0 ± 1.8 (95% CI: 5.4–6.6). No significant difference was observed ($p = 0.661$).

Correlation Analysis

A Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between depressive and anxiety symptom scores ($r = 0.45, p < 0.05, CI: 0.21 - 0.64$). The length of institutional stay was not significantly correlated with depressive symptoms ($r = 0.12, p = 0.386, 95\% CI: -0.15 to 0.39$) or anxiety symptom scores ($r = 0.19, p = 0.215, 95\% CI: -0.10 to -0.48$).

Cluster Analysis and Risk Profiles

A cluster analysis was conducted using the k-means method to identify distinct groups based on symptom severity. The analysis included total scores for anxiety and depressive symptoms as clustering variables.

The first group consisted of $n = (47.4\%)$, characterized by low to moderate levels of both anxiety and depressive symptoms. The second group included $n = 20 (52.6\%)$, who exhibited high anxiety and moderate depressive symptoms. Statistical comparisons between groups revealed that participants in the second group scored significantly higher in anxiety symptoms ($p < 0.05$) but not in depressive

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

symptoms ($p = 0.112$). Additionally, no significant differences were observed between groups in sociodemographic variables, such as sex ($p = 0.238$) or length of institutional stay ($p = 0.321$).

■ DISCUSSION

The strongest finding in this study was the moderate positive correlation between anxiety and depressive symptoms, suggesting a close relationship between these two conditions in foster care children and adolescents. This aligns with established literature emphasizing the high comorbidity of anxiety and depression, particularly in vulnerable populations. The bidirectional nature of this relationship implies that one condition can exacerbate the other, leading to compounded difficulties. This underscores the critical need for integrated screening and intervention strategies that address both disorders simultaneously (Beesdo et al., 2009). Clinically, this finding suggests that even mild depressive symptoms in this population could signal the presence of anxiety and vice versa. Foster care homes should therefore adopt comprehensive mental health assessments to identify overlapping conditions, which may otherwise remain undetected.

Female participants consistently demonstrated higher scores in social anxiety and restlessness compared to males, with these differences reaching statistical significance. These results are consistent with research indicating that females are more vulnerable to anxiety-related conditions due to biological, social, and environmental factors (McLean et al., 2011). The finding that females also scored higher in negative self-esteem further highlights the gendered nature of mental health challenges in institutionalized settings. While no significant gender differences were ob-

served in overall depressive symptoms, the trend in negative self-esteem warrants closer attention.

The cluster analysis revealed two distinct groups: one with low to moderate symptoms and another with high anxiety and moderate depressive symptoms. This subgroup with high anxiety represents a group at elevated risk for long-term mental health complications. Severe anxiety, as observed in this group, has been often linked to impaired social and academic functioning as well as increased risk to develop psychiatric conditions (Costello et al., 2003).

Thus, the identification of such subgroups is critical for prioritizing interventions. Tailored mental health programs should focus on individuals in the high-risk cluster, providing specialized therapeutic support to prevent symptom escalation and improve psychosocial outcomes. However, the lack of significant differences in sociodemographic variables between clusters suggests that symptom severity may be influenced more by institutional factors or individual histories rather than demographic characteristics.

Contrary to expectations, the length of institutional stay was not significantly associated with depressive or anxiety symptoms. While a trend suggested higher anxiety scores with longer stays, the lack of statistical significance highlights the complexity of this relationship. It is possible that other factors, such as the quality of caregiving, past trauma, or individual resilience, may play a more mediating or predicting role in shaping future psychiatric outcomes. This finding emphasizes the importance of improving caregiving practices and providing consistent emotional support within foster care homes. Future studies should explore this relationship further using longitudinal

Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

designs to capture the dynamic interplay between foster care settings and mental health.

■ LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. The small sample size reduces the generalizability of the findings, and the cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data introduces the possibility of response bias, particularly among younger participants. The absence of multivariable analyses to control for potential confounders, such as past trauma or the quality of care, further limits the interpretability of the results. Future research should prioritize larger, longitudinal studies to explore the temporal relationship between institutional factors and mental health outcomes. Incorporating caregiver assessments and observational data could also provide a more comprehensive understanding of the caregiving environment and its impact on children's well-being.

■ CONCLUSION

The study found a moderate positive correlation between anxiety and depressive symptoms, highlighting their frequent comorbidity and the need for integrated screening and intervention strategies. Female participants exhibited significantly higher scores in social anxiety, restlessness, and negative self-esteem, emphasizing the importance of gender-sensitive mental health programs. Cluster analysis identified a high-risk group with severe anxiety and moderate depression, highlighting the need for tailored interventions to prevent long-term consequences. Contrary to expectations, the length of foster care stay was not significantly associated with mental health outcomes. Future research should explore caregiving

quality and trauma history to better understand these dynamics.

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■ CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors lack conflicts of interest to disclose.

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Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

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Prevalence of Psychopathology of Children and Adolescents in Foster Care Homes in Mexico City: An Exploratory Analytic Study

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